

1.0, and nitrofen at 2.0 kg/ha. For early-maturing varieties such as Pusa 33-30, yields were highest with 2,4-D IPE at 1.0 kg/ha, followed by yield with nitrofen. These treatments were statistically similar to the weed-free check and two hand weedings. ■

Leaf scald disease of rice in Sierra Leone

S. A. Raymundo, pathologist. Rice Research Station, Rokupr, Sierra Leone, West Africa

Although leaf scald disease of rice incited by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* has long been present in West Africa, precise information about its economic significance is meager or entirely lacking.

From 1974 to the present the author has worked with the disease in farmers' fields and experimental plots. The following are general conclusions:

1. The disease is most severe in the uplands. Yield reductions from 9 to 12% were estimated from preliminary studies.
2. Severe infection (more than 25% leaf area desiccation) can occur in wet season paddy or irrigated rice. The disease appears insignificant on dry season crops.
3. Visible infection usually appears after the end of tillering. However, the disease has also been found in seedling nurseries.
4. Narrow-leaf varieties like ROK 3, PN 623-3, ADNY 8, and ROK 8 are less affected than broad-leaf varieties like

IRAT 8, Moroberekan, LAC 23, and ROK 16.

5. Broadleaf varieties that retain water droplets on the leaf surface are more susceptible to the disease.

6. The disease is more severe on fertilized than unfertilized plots. This susceptibility under varying soil fertility levels was particularly striking in Sierra Leone's "On Farm Trials" network where upland plots received 60 kg N/ha, 40 kg P/ha, and 40 kg K/ha.

At the Rokupr Rice Research Station, studies on yield loss, epidemiology, plant canopy characteristics, spacing, and fertility levels in relation to disease severity, are in progress. Additionally, varietal screening for total performance including resistance to scald is continuing. ■

Rice diseases during kharif in Karnataka, India

S. Sanne Cowda, pathologist (AICRIP), The University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station, V. C. Farm, Mandya, Karnataka, India

Rice blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* occurs every year in the main rice-growing areas of Karnataka state. Neck blast is usually more damaging than leaf blast. Out of 683 NSN entries screened for blast, only 35 were resistant at Ponnampet during 1978 kharif:

IET6586, IET6731, IET6814, IET6868, IET6873, IET6876, IET6877, IET6880, IET6881, IET6882, IET6883, IET6884, IET6894, IET6899, IET6900, IET6907, IET6914, IET6916, IET6950, IET6951, IET6952, IET4554, IET5905, IET5909, IET5910, IET5911, IET6046, IET6260, IET4699, IET5735, IET6312, IET6663, IET6665, IET6667, and IET6669.

Brown leaf spot (*Helminthosporium oryzae*), the next most important disease, occurs throughout the state.

Udbatta disease (*Ephelis oryzae*) has increased in recent years. Severe infection of high yielding dwarf varieties caused considerable yield loss.

The problems of grain discoloration increased after the introduction of high yielding varieties. The discolored grains are associated with organisms like *P. oryzae*, *Trichoconis oryzae*, and *Dreschlera oryzae*.

Leaf scald due to *Rhynchosporium oryzae* has been observed in the past 7 to 8 years on high yielding varieties.

Other erratic and minor diseases like bacterial leaf blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*), false-smut (*Ustilaginoidea virens*), sheath blight (*Corticium sasakii*), and sheath rot (*Acrocyndrium oryzae*) have also been observed. ■

Acquisition of rice tungro virus through parafilm membrane by *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant)

P. Q. Cabauatan and K. C. Ling, International Rice Research Institute, Philippines

The ability of 547 adult *Nephotettix virescens* to acquire the tungro virus from diseased leaves covered with parafilm was tested. After an acquisition access time of 1 to 4 days, 56 to 75% of the insects became infective on TNI seedlings (see table). In general, the percentage of infective insects increases as the

Percentage of infective *N. virescens* after acquisition feeding on tungro-diseased leaves covered with parafilm. IRRRI, 1979.

Acquisition access time (days)	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (%)
1	221	56
2	197	75
3	89	74
4	40	68

acquisition access time lengthens from 1 to 4 days. But in this test it decreased on the third and fourth day because the diseased leaves became necrotic from continuous insect feeding, and started to decay. The parafilm membrane did not hinder acquisition feeding by the insect. The method may therefore be used for developing a bioassay of the virus. ■

Field efficacy of stable bleaching powder to control bacterial blight of rice

Tara Chand, Nirmaljit Singh, Harnam Singh, and B. S. Thind, Department of Plant Pathology, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141004, Punjab, India

In a field trial during 1977 and 1978 kharif, stable bleaching powder (SBP) was tested for the control of bacterial blight of rice. Seedlings of Jaya were inoculated with a virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda and Ishiyama) Dowson by the clipping method 3 weeks after transplanting. Three 15 kg/ha applications of SBP were spread on fields having 4.5 to 5.0 cm of standing water to provide 10 ppm chlorine. The first application was made 72 hours before inoculation and subsequent applications were at fortnightly intervals. Disease incidence was recorded 2 weeks after the last application; the other observations were

made at harvest (see table).

Application of SBP reduced disease incidence and percentage of chaffy grains. It increased the number of panicle-bearing tillers and total yield over that in the inoculated control. However, differences among various treatments were not significant. SBP is cheaper than other spray chemicals. One or two 15 kg/ha applications during the rainy season, when it is difficult to spray the crop, may help prevent a secondary spread of the pathogen. ■

Effect of soil-applied stable bleaching powder in controlling bacterial blight of rice, av for 2 years, Ludhiana, India, 1977-78.

Applications (no.)	Disease incidence (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Wt (g) of 1000 healthy grains	Chaffiness (%)	Tillers (no./m ²)	
					With panicles	Without panicles
1	50.8	5.6	28.2	25.8	220.5	68.5
2	49.9	5.6	28.8	25.8	223.0	56.5
3	49.6	5.7	28.9	25.6	234.0	52.0
Control (inoculated)	58.9	5.0	28.8	32.7	215.5	73.5
Control (uninoculated)	9.4	6.4	29.3	15.9	272.0	45.0

A survey of South Arcot District in Tamil Nadu for diseases of rice

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India

The rice crop on about 230 ha in 8 villages (Vaniyampalayam, Sundaripalayam, V. Akaram, Kurunthipadi, Pennadam, Mazhikaikottam, Eraiyur, and Erappavur) in South Arcot district of Tamil Nadu was surveyed for rice diseases on 13 and

Disease incidence on 4 varieties of rice, Tamil Nadu, India, 1978.

Variety	Tungro (%)	Brown spot (%)	Sheath rot (%)	Narrow brown leaf spot (%)
IR20	56.3	—	43.2	29.6
BCP 1	17.9	—	11.6	3.4
Co 40	90.7	81.5	31.9	5.9
Ponni	35.2	—	17.4	—

14 December 1978. Rice tungro virus disease had the highest incidence,

followed by sheath rot and narrow brown leaf spot (see table). ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Yield loss due to rice tungro virus

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India

During 1978 kuruvai and samba, a severe incidence of rice tungro virus was observed in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu. A study to estimate yield loss caused by the virus was undertaken. The test variety was the highly susceptible ADT 31. Yields from 100 hills that

Yield losses caused by rice tungro virus, Thanjavur district, India, 1978.

Time (DT) ^a when disease symptoms were observed	Grain yield (g/100 hills)	Yield loss (%)
<i>Diseased plants</i>		
15	8.8	98.5
30	14.8	97.2
45	369.6	30.4
60	490.2	7.5
<i>Healthy plants</i>		
	529.7	

^aDays after transplanting.

showed disease symptoms at 15, 30, 45, and 60 days after transplanting were recorded. The yield from 100 healthy hills was also recorded (see table).

During the year severe tungro disease reduced the yield from some of the PES fields to only 450-700 kg/ha. ■

Attraction of gall midge to lights

S. K. Shrivastava, P. D. Deshmukh, D. J. Pophali, G. A. Gangrade, U. K. Kaushik, B. C. Shukla, and G. L. Patidar. Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, College of Agriculture, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

A 1978 epidemic of *Orseolia oryzae* on kharif paddy in Chattisgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, is suspected to have been caused by the fact that the summer paddy crop (Jan-Jun) was linked with the kharif season, so gall midge is carried over. About 8% of the tillers of the

preceding summer paddy crop harbored gall midge.

A 100-watt electric bulb was fitted at 2-m height near farmhouse walls at both Raipur and Marod. Swarms of gall midge adults attracted to the lights were then caught by hand net. Times of peak catches at both locations were similar. At Marod 2.1% were caught from 1800 to 1900 hours, 22.5% from 1900 to 2000, 29.8% from 2000 to 2100, 27.5% from 2100 to 2200, and 15.5% from 2200 to 2300 (Fig. 1). The majority (87.4%) of the flies were attracted between 1900 to 2300. After that, the catches declined to 8.3% just before midnight. Thus 97.8% of the flies were attracted and caught before midnight.

Peculiarly, at midnight of 29 September, 98% of the flies were attracted between 2000 and 2100 hours. That night 877,500 flies were collected (Fig. 2). Catches declined the next day. Weather conditions (evening temperature